

Emotion Detection from Images Using Machine Learning

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Abstract— Face recognition has been around for years. Taking a step forward, human emotions displayed by the face and felt by the brain can be approximate in either video, electrical signal, or image format. Human emotion recognition is necessary allow modern artificial intelligence systems to emulate and measure facial reactions. The current approaches primarily focus on facial recognition using OpenCV and the training of neural networks for facial expression detection. And the model is trained with TensorFlow, concentrating on some of the most commonly reported facial emotion classes, such as anger, sadness, pleasure, fear, surprise, disgust, and neutral. Facial recognition is divided into many classes in this work. Deep learning is used in the proposed methodology. The data utilized in the analysis came from Google. In terms of accuracy, precision, and recall, the suggested and existing methodologies are compared. The proposed technique outperforms all of the usual evaluation parameters, according to the analysis.

Keywords— face recognition, OpenCV, TensorFlow, Deep learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Faces have an unrivalled role in human social relations. Faces can also be used to acquire information about what other people are thinking or feeling. It is vital to analyze and interpret facial expressions of emotion in order to adjust our social interactions effectively. Since the 1970s, sociological and psychological research has proven that the six most common facial expressions of emotion are universal. Pattern recognition and classification have shown to be particularly beneficial with machine learning techniques. Functionality is the most crucial component of machine learning algorithms. The robustness and nature of classification algorithms, as well as their effectiveness versus various types of datasets, can be investigated using human emotional datasets. The current manuscript focuses on some of the major facial expression classes reported: anger, sadness, smiles, fears, surprises, and neutrality. In this study, the neural network and the model to recognize facial expressions, trained using TensorFlow.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Ninad Mehendale [1] done a study on convolutional neural networks (FERC) to recognize five fundamental facial expression classes: displeasure/anger, sad/unhappy, smiling/happy, scared, and surprised/astonished, with a maximum accuracy of 99.3%.

Corneanu et al., Matusugu et al., and Viola et al. [2,3,4] Using multimodal techniques, a main classification for emotion recognition was established. They largely discussed the procedures and parameters for recognising emotions. Localization of the face employing detection and segmentation using Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) algorithms were among the methods mentioned.

Li et al. [5] stated that emotion identification is entirely based on visual information He carried out an experiment involving the recognition of smiles. The grins were depicted in the subjects. A comparison between 3D and 2D emotion recognition was done. The symmetric property of the face technique was employed for registration to finish the test.

Mohammed et al. [6] Bilateral Two-dimensional Principal Component Analysis (B2DPCA) and an extreme learning machine were used to create a novel algorithm (ELM). A curvelet-based approach was also utilized in addition to these two.

Kahou et al. [7] For emotion recognition, worked on a hybrid CNN—RNN (Recurrent Neural Network) design. Aggregation of CNN and RNN was used to create the hybrid technique.

III. MOTIVATION

The face is one of the most relevant social incentives because it conveys essential information in the process of social interaction and communication. Facial expressions, in particular, communicate information about the emotions that the target is experiencing. This has an impact on how the target is viewed and what behavioral inclinations the observer is activated by. As a result, it has been demonstrated in this research that correctly identifying others' emotions is positively related to successful social functioning and adversely related to loneliness. The importance of correctly perceiving the emotions on another person's face necessitates a thorough examination of the components that influence facial emotion identification. The purpose of this study is to address the aforementioned factors.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to detect the emotion through the facial expressions using a machine learning model. Where in this, the facial recognition is done into several

classes. The proposed methodology is based on deep learning. In other words, the current approach primarily focuses on facial recognition using OpenCV. The training of neural network . and model for facial expression detection is done using TensorFlow

The structure is:

Figure 1: Emotion Detection Methodology

The steps that require to be followed are:

1. Data Collection
2. Data Pre-processing
3. Model Building
4. Summary Check
5. Result

Data Collection: This study was well-reviewed, and it employed a good dataset to avoid overfitting to a regularly used benchmark dataset's test set. Using the Google image search API, researchers looked for photos of faces that matched a set of 184 emotion-related keywords like "blissful," "enraged," and so on. The first 1000 photos returned for each query were saved for the next round of processing. Using OpenCV face recognition, bounding boxes around each face in the collected pictures were created. The classification at a finer level. TensorFlow

combines a variety of methods and models to allow users to build deep neural networks for applications such as image identification and classification, as well as natural language processing.

A. Once the images were accepted and cropped to 48x48 pixels, gray scaled and scaled to 48x48 pixels, emotion keywords were mapped into the same seven major categories. There are 4953 "Anger" images, 547 "Disgust" images, 5121 "Fear" photographs, 8989 "Happiness" images, 6077 "Sadness" images, 4002 "Surprise" images, and 6198 "Neutral" images in the final dataset.

B. Data Pre-processing: This is the first stage in any machine learning algorithm. Cleaning, transformation, and minimization of data are all part of this process. This all are done to make the data more effective. The data can be processed to make our model more accurate. So that the classification will be correct.

a) Cleaning Data – In the training dataset, the null values were deleted. A few columns in the dataset were removed because they were useless for the feature selection procedure. For the prediction, pre-processed data was saved. As a result, a usable training dataset was obtained.

b) Splitting of Data – After the data has been formatted, it is divided into training and testing datasets. After that, we use the data we chose for training to train our model.

C. Machine Learning: This is used to detect the emotion through facial recognition. The machine learning algorithms are used to detect human emotions, that will check the facial reactions. There are several techniques present to detect the facial emotions. The solution accuracy relies on how it is trained.

a) OpenCV- Basically OpenCV's points of strength are in the deployment side. To recognize faces in photographs, we will first conduct face detection, then use deep learning to extract the face embeddings from each face, and lastly train a face recognition model on the embeddings to recognize faces in the photos.

b) Tensor Flow - Training of neural networks and base model for facial expression detection is done using Tensor Flow in this paper. TensorFlow's points of strength are in the training side. It has pre- trained models that easily help with image. TensorFlow is a deep learning library developed by Google and available as an open-source library. Machine learning is also offered by TensorFlow. TensorFlow was designed for large numerical computations rather than deep learning. It proved to be quite beneficial for deep learning, thus Google decided to make it open-source. TensorFlow accepts data in the form of tensors, which are higher-dimensional multi-dimensional arrays. Multi-dimensional arrays are useful for dealing with large volume of data

D. Summary Check – The summary check in the

base model is done in order to crisscross that everything is coming out right or not. In this task, it is done in an appropriate way to avoid issues of overfitting. And the summary checker for the model in this paper showed proper working of the it.

IV. BUILD MODEL

The main stage in detecting emotions is to develop a model. The algorithms are used when creating the model.. The steps involved are:

1.Import the packages that are necessary.

```
import os
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import tensorflow as tf
from matplotlib import pyplot
```

```
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
```

2.Add the data into a DataFrame, then get the shape of data.

```
[ ] df= pd.read_csv('fer2013/fer2013.csv')
df.head()
```

	emotion	pixels	Usage
0	0	70 80 82 72 58 58 60 63 54 58 60 48 89 115 121...	Training
1	0	151 150 147 155 148 133 111 140 170 174 182 15...	Training
2	2	231 212 156 164 174 138 161 173 182 200 106 38...	Training
3	4	24 32 36 30 32 23 19 20 30 41 21 22 32 34 21 1...	Training
4	6	4 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 3 15 23 28 48 50 58 84...	Training

3.Then split the dataset into training and testing datasets in a 90:10 ratio.

```
X_train,X_test,y_train,y_test = train_test_split(img_array,labes,test_size=.1)
```

4.After that create base model using TensorFlow by defining all of the layers, input shape and output shape.

```
from matplotlib.cbook import flatten
base_model = tf.keras.models.Sequential([
    tf.keras.layers.Conv2D(32, (3, 3), activation='relu', input_shape=(48,48,1)),
    tf.keras.layers.MaxPool2D(2,2),
    tf.keras.layers.BatchNormalization(),
    #
    tf.keras.layers.Conv2D(64, (3, 3), activation='relu', input_shape=(48,48,1)),
    tf.keras.layers.MaxPool2D(2,2),
    tf.keras.layers.BatchNormalization(),
    #
    tf.keras.layers.Conv2D(128, (3, 3), activation='relu', input_shape=(48,48,1)),
    tf.keras.layers.MaxPool2D(2,2),
    tf.keras.layers.BatchNormalization(),
    #
    tf.keras.layers.Flatten(),
    tf.keras.layers.Dense(128, activation='relu'),
    tf.keras.layers.Dense(7, activation='softmax')
])
```

5.After each declaration check the summary of the base

model to analyze that everything is coming correct or not

```
base_model.summary()
```

6.Then compile the base model

```
base_model.compile(optimizer=tf.keras.optimizers.RMSprop(learning_rate=.0001),
loss='sparse_categorical_crossentropy',
metrics=['accuracy'])
```

7. Add a callback method to each iteration to check validation accuracy.

```
call_back = tf.keras.callbacks.ModelCheckpoint(filepath=checkpoint_path,
monitor='val_accuracy',
verbose=1,
save_freq='epoch',
save_best_only=True,
save_weights_only=False,
mode='max')
```

8.Then create a folder using os to place the trained model

```
import os
os.mkdir('checkpoint')
```

9.After all this start the training of the base model

```
[ ] base_model.fit(X_train,y_train,epochs=20,validation_split=.9,callbacks=call_back)
```

10. Then after the training start the prediction based on it with maximum accuracy

```
final_model = tf.keras.models.load_model(checkpoint_path)
from IPython.display import clear_output
import time
for k in range(40):
    print(f'actual label is {label_to_text[y_test[k]]}')
    predicted_class = final_model.predict(tf.expand_dims(X_test[k], 0)).argmax()
    print(f'predicted label is {label_to_text[predicted_class]}')
    pyplot.imshow(X_test[k].reshape((48,48)))
    pyplot.show()
    time.sleep(5)
    clear_output(wait=True)
```

V. RESULT

The results reveal that in terms of accuracy, precision, and recall, the facial emotions on the photos are correctly predicted, and the suggested technique outperforms all of the

traditional assessment metrics.

actual label is surprise
predicted label is surprise

... actual label is happiness
predicted label is happiness

... actual label is neutral
predicted label is neutral

VI.

CONCLUSION

The current approach primarily focuses on facial recognition using OpenCV, and the training of neural networks and model for facial expression detection is done using TensorFlow.

The current paper study focuses on some of the crucial facial expression classes reported, which are anger, sadness, happiness, fear, surprise, disgust and neutral.

In this study emotion detection is divided into several classes. And deep learning is being used in the proposed methodology. The collected data in the analysis sourced from Google. In terms of accuracy, precision, and recall, the suggested and existing methodologies are compared. The result of the study shows that the proposed technique beats all of the usual evaluation parameters.

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